

Towards Distribution Transparency for Supervised ML With Oblivious Training Functions

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ABSTRACT

Building and productionizing Machine Learning (ML) models is a process of interdependent steps of iterative code updates, including exploratory model design, hyperparameter tuning, ablation experiments, and model training. Industrial-strength ML involves doing this at scale, using many compute resources, and this requires rewriting the training code to account for distribution. The result is that moving from a single host program to a cluster hinders iterative development of the software, as iterative development would require multiple versions of the software to be maintained and kept consistent. In this paper, we introduce the distribution oblivious training function as an abstraction for ML development in Python, whereby developers can reuse the same training function when running a notebook on a laptop or performing scale-out hyperparameter search and distributed training on clusters. Programs written in our framework look like industry-standard ML programs as we factor out dependencies using best-practice programming idioms (such as functions to generate models and data batches). We believe that our approach takes a step towards unifying single-host and distributed ML development.

1 INTRODUCTION

Machine learning (ML) is a complex subject, and the process of learning to program (train) ML applications usually involves starting with the simplest possible program, avoiding complexities such as feature engineering and scalability (distributed programming), and slowly adding complexity over time. In particular, moving from single-host applications to distributed applications is challenging, especially for supervised ML as it requires rewriting entire applications. This keeps many developers, who are used to single host debugging and testing and have limited knowledge about distributed environments, from discovering the benefits of distributed ML: faster hyperparameter sweeps and reduced training times.

The contribution of this paper is the design and implementation a framework that unifies single-host and distributed training functions based on an abstraction we call the *distribution oblivious training function*. We make training functions reusable by following the dependency inversion principle [6] to factor out those aspects of training functions that are subject to change between single-host and distributed applications. We demonstrate our framework for

Keras/TensorFlow (TF) programs, but the approach generalizes to other frameworks that support distribution, such as PyTorch.

2 DISTRIBUTION TRANSPARENCY IN ML

Figure 1: Inner and outer loops for the training function

Transparency in distributed systems [8] refers to hiding distribution-specific aspects of an application from the developer - for example, a developer invoking a function may not know (or need to know) if the function she is calling is local to her application or on a remote server. Distribution transparency enables developers to write code that is reusable between single-host and distributed instantiations of a program.

In supervised ML, the core logic that is common across all programs is the training function - a series of steps including defining a model architecture, then ingesting labelled training data and feeding it to the model and iterating until some termination (or convergence) criteria are met. The output of the training function is a model that can be used to make predictions on new data, drawn from the same distribution as the training data.

Training functions, however, can be used in many different contexts when we distribute supervised ML programs: single host notebooks, distributed hyperparameter search, parallel ablation studies, and distributed training are common examples. However, existing frameworks for supervised ML, such as Keras/TensorFlow and PyTorch, require training functions to be rewritten to account for the distribution strategy, what accelerators the computations are scheduled on, and whether the optimizer needs to share its results with other hosts (for distributed training). In figure 1, we illustrate how training functions can be used - as part of (1) *the inner loop* when the same training function is either run on a single host or on many hosts in parallel (as part of data-parallel distributed training) using (distributed) stochastic gradient descent, or (2) *the outer loop* when the training function is run on different hosts for example

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Table 1: Distributed aspects of the training function that need to be re-written for different distributed contexts

Process Step	Distributed aspects of the Training Function
HParam Search	Model Architecture, Hyperparameters, Early Stopping, Optimizer, Regularization
Ablation Study	Model Architecture, Features (Input Data), Regularization, Optimizer
Distributed Training	Features (Input Data), Optimizer, Accelerator-awareness

with different hyperparameters for each host, and a global optimizer that collects the results of hyperparameter trials to decide on subsequent trials, searching for better hyperparameters.

Table 1 lists the aspects of training functions in Keras/TensorFlow that need to be rewritten for a distribution context, compared to the single-host Python program. For the inner loop, the hyperparameters and model architecture can vary, and code needs to be rewritten to account for how many hardware accelerators are being used. For the outer loop, the variable aspects related to model configuration are controlled by a global optimizer, such as a Bayesian optimizer proposing different configurations (trials), or an ablator, generating trials by leaving one or more components out at a time. The trials can be run in parallel on a cluster and the results collected by a global optimizer or ablator.

3 DISTRIBUTION OBLIVIOUS TRAINING FUNCTION

Figure 2: ML model development process

In figure 2, we can see how developers structure their applications to write *distribution oblivious training functions* and include them in the different distribution contexts. Firstly, developers write the common training function, and as is now considered good ML engineering practice, developers also write separate functions for model architecture generation and data batch reading. The training function becomes a parameterizable higher order function with generator functions and hyperparameter configurations as input. For hyperparameter search, a search space needs to be defined from which a global optimizer (can be user-defined) draws the hyperparameters from, but for other cases, the hyperparameters are fixed. For example, the final distributed training step should make use of the best configuration found in the previous search experiments.

The distribution context and environment can be initialized outside the training function (it is oblivious to it) to make appropriate use of the resources such as accelerators. Other means to achieve transparency of the two loops include the use of pluggable hooks, such as the Keras/TF callbacks.

4 UNIFIED EXECUTION FRAMEWORK WITH JUPYTER NOTEBOOKS ON HOPSWORKS

With Hopsworks [4] and the Maggy framework [1][7], we provide a unified development and execution framework for distribution transparent Jupyter notebooks [5]. That is, the developer writes a Jupyter notebook that can be run/debugged using a single host Python kernel, and the same notebook can also be run on a cluster using many hosts and hardware accelerators as a PySpark application. The developer only needs to set a distribution context parameter that controls which cells to run in the notebook - the oblivious training function is a single cell used by all the different distribution contexts. The notebooks can also be parameterized and run by an external workflow manager (Airflow) in production ML pipelines, similar to Papermill by Netflix [9].

5 RELATED WORK

Previous work on this topic can be categorized in three dimensions: Pipeline orchestration, ML lifecycle management and automated ML (AutoML). Pipeline orchestration covers the aspect of taking an entire ML pipeline into production, which includes data preparation and engineering, modeling, training, serving inference and managing the deployments. TensorFlow Extended (TFX) [2] is a TF based platform with the goal of minimizing glue code between these pipeline steps. Compared to the previous category, ML lifecycle management is concerned with the iterative nature of the ML development process. By tracking artifacts, logs and experiments, results can be easily reproduced, making the process more transparent with respect to the trained models themselves. MLFlow [10] achieves this by allowing the user to make explicit calls to log this meta-data. AutoML aims to automate every aspect of the pipeline. However, due to the high computational requirements, recent work was focusing on the automation of the separate steps first. Because many parts of a ML model behave like a black-box and can be encoded in hyperparameters, one can fall back on search for optimization of such parameters [3].

6 SUMMARY

In this short paper, we introduced the distribution oblivious training function for supervised ML and showed how it can be used to write distribution transparent ML programs. In the Hopsworks platform, this provides developers with a unified framework and codebase where Jupyter notebooks can first be developed as single-host Python programs, then extended to distributed contexts, and iterative development across single-host and distributed versions is not just possible, but encouraged. The distribution oblivious training function can have several benefits for ML systems. It can (1) enable reductions in technical debt in pipeline orchestration, (2) enable iterative development between laptops and clusters, and (3) improve model training lifecycle management by factoring out explicit logging calls from user code.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Logical Clocks AB. 2020. *Maggy: Asynchronous Distributed Hyperparameter Optimization Based on Apache Spark*. Logical Clocks AB. Retrieved January 15th, 2020 from <https://github.com/logicalclocks/maggy>
- [2] Denis Baylor, Eric Breck, Heng-Tze Cheng, Noah Fiedel, Chuan Yu Foo, Zakaria Haque, Salem Haykal, Mustafa Ispir, Vihan Jain, Levent Koc, et al. 2017. TFx: A tensorflow-based production-scale machine learning platform. In *Proceedings of the 23rd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. ACM, 1387–1395.
- [3] Frank Hutter, Lars Kotthoff, and Joaquin Vanschoren (Eds.). 2018. *Automated Machine Learning: Methods, Systems, Challenges*. Springer. In press, available at <http://automl.org/book>.
- [4] Mahmoud Ismail, Ermias Gebremeskel, Theofilos Kakantousis, Gautier Berthou, and Jim Dowling. 2017. Hopsworks: Improving User Experience and Development on Hadoop with Scalable, Strongly Consistent Metadata. In *2017 IEEE 37th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS)*. IEEE, 2525–2528.
- [5] Thomas Kluyver, Benjamin Ragan-Kelley, Fernando Pérez, Brian E Granger, Matthias Bussonnier, Jonathan Frederic, Kyle Kelley, Jessica B Hamrick, Jason Grout, Sylvain Corlay, et al. 2016. Jupyter Notebooks-a publishing format for reproducible computational workflows.. In *ELPUB*. 87–90.
- [6] Robert C Martin. 2002. *Agile software development: principles, patterns, and practices*. Prentice Hall.
- [7] Moritz Johannes Meister. 2019. *Maggy: Open-Source Asynchronous Distributed Hyperparameter Optimization Based on Apache Spark*. Master's thesis.
- [8] Andrew S Tanenbaum and Maarten Van Steen. 2007. *Distributed systems: principles and paradigms*. Prentice-Hall.
- [9] April Yi Wang, Anant Mittal, Christopher Brooks, and Steve Oney. 2019. How Data Scientists Use Computational Notebooks for Real-Time Collaboration. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 3, CSCW (2019), 1–30.
- [10] Matei Zaharia, Andrew Chen, Aaron Davidson, Ali Ghodsi, Sue Ann Hong, Andy Konwinski, Siddharth Murching, Tomas Nykodym, Paul Ogilvie, Mani Parkhe, et al. 2018. Accelerating the Machine Learning Lifecycle with MLflow. *IEEE Data Eng. Bull.* 41, 4 (2018), 39–45.

¹Project website: <http://earthanalytics.eu>.